

Table S1. Characteristics of the 126 DMRs used as markers in the epiRILs in the CpG context.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
epiRIL	published <i>ddm1</i> markers	published col-wt markers	EM-seq verified <i>ddm1</i> markers	EM-seq verified col-wt markers	Total verified markers	%similarity with published data	Markers that change	<i>ddm1</i> markers that switch to methylated	wt markers that switch to hypomethylated	hypermethylated markers	<i>ddm1</i> markers that switch to methylated	wt markers that switch to hypomethylated	hypermethylated markers	verified <i>ddm1</i> markers
11	16	110	5	103	108	85,7	18	11	5	2	330, 371, 372, 373, 374*, 378, 379, 380, 382, 383*, 385	87, 166, 171, 240, 495	371, 716	1, 2, 335, 357, 679
24	11	115	10	112	122	96,8	4	1	3	0	544	17, 495, 531		1, 2, 4, 392, 414, 415, 699, 701, 703, 704
60	44	82	33	78	111	88,1	15	11	3	1	91, 114, 372, 373, 374*, 378, 379, 380, 382, 383*, 385	150, 495, 703	716	25, 27, 33, 39, 52, 58, 87, 101, 123, 126, 166, 167, 550, 551, 552, 553, 586, 587, 654, 661, 665, 666, 678, 679, 686, 691, 69, 694, 695, 698, 699, 701
73	18	108	18	103	121	96,0	5	0	5	0		1, 2, 87, 398, 495	716	550, 551, 665, 666, 678, 679, 686, 689, 691, 693, 694, 695, 698, 699, 701, 703, 704
92	67	59	52	52	104	82,5	22	15	5	2	114, 157, 158, 159, 160, 330, 371, 372, 823, 827, 832, 837, 849, 853, 854	398, 495, 698, 701, 703	371, 827	661, 665, 666, 678, 679, 706, 707, 712, 715, 716, 718, 719, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825, 845
95	38	88	30	84	114	90,5	12	8	3	1	706, 823, 827, 832, 837, 849, 853, 854	87, 385, 495	371	550, 686, 689, 691, 693, 694, 695, 698, 699, 701, 703, 704, 707, 712, 713, 715, 716, 718, 719, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825
101	43	83	33	78	111	88,1	15	11	4	0	7, 114, 126, 823, 827, 832, 837, 845, 849, 853, 854	52, 150, 495, 531		4, 5, 10, 12, 17, 20, 25, 27, 33, 39, 58, 101, 123, 128, 706, 707, 712, 713, 715, 716, 718, 719, 721, 722, 725, 726, 728, 731, 34, 744, 825
108	13	113	11	109	120	95,2	6	2	4	0	396, 398	87, 495, 654, 661		392, 396, 550, 551, 552, 553, 586, 587, 665, 666, 678, 679
118	42	84	29	82	111	88,1	15	14	0	1	7, 91, 114, 157, 158, 159, 160, 418, 466, 515, 527, 529, 537, 544		716	1, 2, 4, 5, 10, 11, 12, 17, 20, 25, 27, 33, 39, 52, 58, 87, 101, 123, 126, 128, 147, 150, 414, 415, 427, 432, 495, 499, 531
150	58	68	28	65	93	73,8	33	30	2	1	114, 157, 158, 159, 160, 163, 383*, 385, 388, 402, 405*, 515, 527, 529, 537*, 546*, 547*, 823, 827, 832, 837, 845, 849, 853, 854, 859, 862, 863, 865, 867	398, 495	716	101, 123, 126, 128, 147, 150, 399, 400, 531, 550, 551, 552, 553, 586, 587, 654, 661, 665, 666, 678, 679, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825
193	58	68	39	66	105	83,3	21	19	0	2	330, 371, 372, 373, 374, 378, 379, 380, 402, 418, 466, 499, 515, 527, 529, 537, 544, 546*, 547*		371, 827	686, 689, 691, 693,
195	7	119	6	111	117	92,9	9	1	8	0	665, 661	87, 495, 550, 551, 553, 587, 654		427, 432, 666, 678, 679, 686
202	31	95	27	90	117	92,9	9	4	4	1	114, 158, 159, 160	150, 495, 531, 694	716	17, 20, 25, 27, 33, 39, 52, 58, 87, 101, 123, 550, 551, 552, 553, 586, 587, 654, 661, 665, 666, 678, 679, 686, 689, 691, 693
215	27	99	9	96	105	83,3	21	18	2	1	157, 158, 159, 160, 163, 330, 367, 371, 372, 373, 374*, 378, 379, 380, 382, 383*, 385, 388	87, 495	371	147, 150, 166, 167, 168, 171, 240, 335, 357
232	96	30	70	26	96	76,2	30	27	2	1	7, 330, 371, 372, 373, 374*, 388, 418, 466, 515, 527, 529, 537*, 544, 546*, 547*, 827, 832, 837*, 849, 853, 854, 859, 862, 863, 865, 867	150, 385	371	396, 398, 399, 400, 402, 405, 414, 415, 427, 432, 495, 499, 531, 550, 551, 552, 553, 586, 587, 654, 661, 706, 707, 712,
257	48	78	26	75	101	80,2	25	22	3	0	383*, 385, 388, 527, 529, 537*, 544, 546*, 547*, 689, 719*, 823, 827, 832, 837*, 845*, 849, 853, 854, 859*, 862, 863	1, 87, 495		531, 678, 679, 686, 691, 693, 694, 695, 698, 699, 701, 703, 704, 715, 716, 718, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825
260	11	115	10	113	123	97,6	3	1	2	0	388	1, 495		392, 701, 703, 713, 715, 716, 718, 719, 721, 722
											157, 158, 159, 160, 163, 371, 372, 373, 374*, 378, 379, 380, 382, 383*, 388, 418, 427, 466, 499, 515, 527, 529, 531,			
333	64	62	27	60	87	69,0	39	37	1	1	537*, 544, 546, 547*, 823, 827, 832, 837*, 845*, 849, 853, 854, 859*, 862	335	371	357, 392, 396, 398, 399, 400, 402, 405, 414, 415, 432, 495, 706, 707, 712, 713, 715, 716, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825
350	65	61	47	58	105	83,3	21	19	2	0	7, 114, 126, 157, 158, 159, 160, 402, 418, 466, 515, 527, 529, 537*, 544, 823, 827, 832, 837	712, 713		432, 495, 499, 531, 706, 718, 719, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825
361	23	103	19	99	118	93,7	8	5	3	0	4, 7, 91, 114, 128	150, 495, 531		1, 2, 5, 10, 11, 12, 17, 20, 25, 27, 33, 39, 52, 58, 87, 101, 123, 126, 147
366	35	91	25	88	113	89,7	13	10	3		718, 823, 827, 832, 837*, 849, 853, 854, 859*, 862	87, 385, 495		693, 694, 695, 698, 699, 701, 703, 704, 707, 712, 713, 715, 716, 719, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728, 731, 734, 744, 825, 845
371	6	120	6	110	116	92,1	10	0	9	1		87, 166, 167, 495, 553, 586, 587, 666, 694	716	392, 396, 398, 399, 691, 693
480	3	123	0	114	114	90,5	12	3	9	0	863, 865, 867	87, 392, 713, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728		
495	2	124	1	115	116	92,1	10	1	9	0	547	87, 495, 713, 721, 722, 724, 725, 726, 728		392

For each epiRIL (column one) the number of published DMR markers 22 are divided into those inherited from the *ddm1* mutant (hypomethylated) (column two) and those inherited from the Columbia wild type (Col-wt) (methylated), which are in column three. In column four, we display the number of *ddm1* markers found in our analysis of EM-seq data that were called "verified *ddm1* markers" and in the column five, we show the number of verified Col-wt markers. Column six presents the sum of verified *ddm1* and Col-wt markers, which we called "total verified markers". Then, using this number we calculated the percentage similarity with the published data, which is shown in column seven. In column eight, we display the number of markers that changed. In column nine we detail the number of *ddm1* markers that switched from hypomethylated back to methylated as in Col-wt (whose names are shown in column twelve); in column ten we show the Col-wt markers that switched to hypomethylated (whose names are shown in column thirteen); and in column eleven we show the markers that switched to hypermethylated and became different from Col-wt (whose names are shown in column fourteen). *Markers shown in blue are those that contain a potentially mobile transposable element, according to Colomé-Tatché et al. 24.